

The Geographical Study of Slums in Dagon Myothit (East) Township: The Case of Ward 1

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Plate 1: The Slum Settlement in the dumping ground in Ward 1 of

Dagon Myothit (East) Township

Abstract

Ward No. 1 is bounded on the north by North Okkalapa Township, the populated township and on the west by Dagon Myothit (North) Township, the new township. Its northern part is an extended area. Many informal settlements are found in this extended area. It has a population of 9352 and 1909 households in 2017. It has 282 slum households and 1283 slum dwellers. This paper studies the slums from geographical point of view. A slum is a heavily populated urban informal settlement characterized by substandard housing and squalor. The objectives of the paper are to locate the slum in the Ward, study what are the reasons for developing of slums in the study area and analyze social and economical attributes of slums in urban area. In order to achieve these, secondary data are recorded from General Administrative Office of Dagon Myothit (East) Township and primary data are collected by questionnaire in March 2017. This questionnaire includes the questions for gathering information of head of the family, living duration in huts and occupational structure of the slum society, and push and pull factors for the emergence and growth of slums.

Introduction

Dagon Myothit (East) Township is located in East Yangon District. Dagon Myothit (East) Township has 63 wards and 3 villages. People have settled in 29 wards and 3 villages. Slum settlement is also found in these wards and villages. Ward 1 has a population of 9352 and 1909 households and it has 282 slum households and 1283 slum dwellers in 2017 (Figure 1). Ward 1 is selected as the study area because its slum density is higher than the population density. Definition for slum has been defined by many scholars. In this research, the researcher uses the definition of UN-Habitat, 2003. Slums are

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people living under substandard conditions and squalor. This paper focuses on slum settlement from the socio-economic point of view. It has six parts: (1) Introduction, (2) Data and Methodology, (3) Geographical and historical background of the study area, (4) Results and findings, (5) Conclusion and (6) Discussion and Suggestions.

Research problem is the reason why they become homeless people and how to improve their capacities

The aim of the research is to analyse the responsible factors for the emergence and growth of slums in Dagon Myothit (East) Township

Objectives of the research paper is to study the Dependency Ratio in slum area, to focus on the educational level of head of the family as education is the basic parameter in the progress of the society and to study controlling factors on the income of the family

Hypotheses

- The number of school children depends on the income of the family, income and education background of the head of the family, the number of workers in the family, and expenditures.
- The income of the family depends on income of the head of the family, educational background of the head and the number of workers in the family.

Figure 1 : The Distribution of Slums in the Wards and Villages of Dagon Myothit (East) Township, Yangon Region and Location of Ward No. 1

Source : General Administrative Office in Dagon Myothit (East) Township and field survey in 2017

Data and Methodology

Data

Secondary data such as the numbers of population, the number of slums and locality of the study area are recorded from General Administrative Office in Dagon Myothit (East) Township.

Base map for Ward 1 is drawn on the basis of Google image 2017 and field survey in 2017.

Primary data such as information of the head of the family, age structure and labour force, pull and push factors for the emergence and growth of slums in the study area and future expectation of the slums are collected by field survey.

Methodology

In Ward 1 three data sets are collected by structured interview method.

Data set I provides information on the head of the family relating to age of the head, his educational background, occupation and his income.

Data set II includes information of the slum families relating to age structure, the number of workers, the number of school-age children, the number of school children and the size of the family.

Data set III gives push and pull factors for the emergence and growth of slum.

Population density and slum density of Ward 1 are drawn and calculated by ArcMap 10. There are 282 slum households and 1283 (total number of slums) in which 39 slum dwellers were interviewed by systematic sampling method and the need of the field survey. Then, database of three data sets is constructed in Access Database. Dependency ratio and labour force participation rate are calculated by some of the mathematical equations. The relationship between income of the family, income of the head of the family and educational background of the head is calculated by Pearson correlation using SPSS. The link between the number of school children, income of the family, information of the head, and the number of workers in the family is analyzed by Multivariate analysis (path analysis). The emergence and growth of slums is interpreted by qualitative analysis (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Flow Chart of the Study of Slum Area

Source: Researcher's survey

Geographical and Historical Background of the Study Area

The study area, Ward 1, is located between North Latitudes $16^{\circ} 54' 14''$ and $16^{\circ} 55' 1''$, and between East Longitudes $96^{\circ} 11' 24''$ and $96^{\circ} 11' 42''$ (Figure 3). It has an area of 0.767 sq. km (189.5291 acres). The shape of Ward 1 is rectangular. It is situated on south of North Okkalapa Township, the southwestern part of Ngamoeyeik Creek, and on the northeastern part of Dagon Myothit (North) Township. Ward 1 includes Anawrahta Street, Satsantun Street, Nyaung U Phee Street, Land inside Yazathingyan Street and No. 4 Basic Education Primary School.

Ward 1 was established in August 1994 according to the order of Ministry of Home Affairs. General Administrative Department of Dagon Myothit (East) Township was opened on September 1994. In 1997 the ward was extended to the north. Now it includes two parts such as the former Ward 1 and Extended Ward 1. A large area inside three converging streets, Kyansitthar, Anawratha and Yazathingyan Streets, is the extended part of Ward 1. The northern part of the extended area is the dumping ground where 54 slum households are dwelling (Plate 2 and 3).

Figure 3 : The Location of Ward 1 and its Slum Settlement Pattern

Source : Field Survey in 2017

Plate 2: The Slum Settlement in the dumping ground in Ward 1 of Dagon Myothit (East) Township

Plate 3: The Slum Settlement near the dumping ground in Ward 1 of Dagon Myothit (East) Township

Results and Findings

Objective 1

To study the Dependency Ratios and Labour Force Participation Rate in slum area, some of the mathematical equations are used. They are as follow:

$$\text{Child Dependency Ratio (CDR)} = \frac{\text{Total Number of Children of 15-59 year age group}}{\text{Total Population in between 15-59 year age group}} \times 100$$

$$\text{Aged Dependency Ratio (ADR)} = \frac{\text{Total Number of Population above 60 year age group}}{\text{Total Population in between 15-59 year age group}} \times 100$$

$$\text{Dependency Ratio (DR)} = \frac{\text{Children below 14} + \text{population above 60}}{\text{Total Population in between 15-59 year age group}} \times 100$$

$$\text{Labour Force Participation Rate (LFPR)} = \frac{\text{Total Number of Workers between 15 - 59 year age group}}{\text{Total Number of Population}} \times 100$$

Demographic profile in Ward 1 is compared to that of Nairobi, Kenya. Child dependency ratio (CDR) is 66.92% in the study area. It accords with the CDR of Nairobi, 75.8%.

Aged dependency ratio (ADR) is 6.15% and that of Nairobi is 5.1%. CDR in Nairobi is higher than that of CDR in Ward 1 of Dagon Myothit (East) Township and it is opposite true in ADR. This result shows

that Nairobi has more labour force for the future than in Dagon Myothit (East) Township. However, total dependency ratio in Nairobi, Kenya, 80.9%, is higher than in that of Ward 1, 73.8%. Dependency ratio of both slum areas is very high. Therefore, the government needs to solve this unemployment problem.

The labour force participation rate is calculated as the labour force divided by the total number of population. Labour force, the working population, refers to people aged 15 to 59. Labour force participation rate in Ward 1 is 29.33%. This low rate invites immediately policy intervention for poverty.

Objective 2

Education is the basic parameter in the progress of the society. So, it is to focus on the educational level of head of the family.

Hypothesis 1

- The number of school children depends on the income of the family, income and education background of the head of the family, the number of workers in the family, and expenditures.

Related to the method of causal modeling is path analysis, now being widely used in sociological research (Duncan, 1975). This attempt is to identify the relative strengths of the various direct and indirect links between two variables. There are direct and indirect links, and each of the four independent variables, X_1 , X_3 , X_4 and X_5 , simply has a direct effect on the dependent variable, the number of school children (X_0) (Table 2). Poverty stricken parents keeps children from school because they can't survive continued children's support.. Therefore, the researcher is interested in the controlling factors for the number of school children. It needs to know all of school-age children go to school or not.

Multivariate analysis (Path analysis)

X_0 = the number of school children

X_1 = income of the head of the family

X_2 = educational background of the head

X_3 = the number of workers in the family

X_4 = expenditures

X_5 = income of the family

Figure 4 : A Predicted Set of hypothesis for a dependent variable, X_0

Source : Table 1

There is a positive link between the number of school children, X_0 and income of the head of the family, X_1 . It is known that if the number of workers in the family increases, the income will increase and then the number of students will rise. So, correlation coefficients describe the linear relationship between the number of workers in the family, expenditures and income of the family and X_0 respectively. They have a positive link (Figure 4). However, correlations are measures of linear association. Two variables can be related positively or negatively, but if the relationship is not a straight forward, a correlation coefficient is not an appropriate result for assessing their association.

The correlation coefficient between the number of school children and the education background of the head of the family is -0.051. A study shows a low negative correlation: as education level of the head decreases, the number of school-age children increases. Therefore, it needs to compute the partial correlation coefficients to know one or more controlling variables. When income of the head, the number of workers, expenditures and income of the family are considered as control variables, the coefficient increases the observed negative correlation -0.107. Income of the head (X_1) only appears to be negatively related, -0.063. However, the negative correlation is in decreasing because status of the head may influence children's education. These statistics are shown in Table 3 and Table 4. So, it needs to improve the income and education status of head of the family.

Table 1: Information of the head of the family and family members in Ward 1, DME

Source: Field survey in 2017

ID	X_0/X_5 No. of school children	X_1 income head	X_2 education of head	X_3 No. of workers	X_4 expenditure of the family	X_5/X_0 income of the family
1	4	120000	1	1	130000	120000
2	3	300000	3	1	270000	300000
3	2	300000	6	2	200000	200000
4	1	300000	8	3	270000	270000
5	2	150000	4	2	270000	270000
6	2	150000	6	2	200000	250000
7	1	300000	10	1	150000	250000
9	1	200000	1	2	300000	300000
10	1	100000	4	2	300000	300000
11	0	150000	4	3	200000	300000
12	5	600000	1	6	500000	600000
13	2	170000	3	2	300000	300000
14	2	150000	7	1	300000	150000
15	1	120000	4	1	180000	150000
16	4	300000	10	2	300000	300000
17	0	150000	8	1	150000	270000

ID	X_0/X_5 No. of school children	X_1 income head	X_2 education of head	X_3 No. of workers	X_4 expenditure of the family	X_5/X_0 income of the family
18	1	150000	4	1	150000	150000
19	2	110000	0	1	150000	150000
20	1	90000	3	2	90000	90000
21	3	150000	8	2	150000	150000
22	7	30000	4	1	100000	300000
23	0	100000	2	1	80000	100000
24	3	40000	7	3	80000	120000
25	1	180000	4	3	250000	250000
26	1	90000	4	3	150000	150000
27	0	200000	9	1	200000	200000
28	1	200000	9	1	250000	200000
29	2	150000	10	2	250000	300000
30	4	150000	10	3	300000	300000
31	1	150000	10	2	350000	300000
32	0	45000	4	2	100000	100000
33	1	180000	4	2	250000	250000
34	0	120000	2	3	200000	200000
35	1	180000	4	1	150000	150000
36	2	120000	10	2	300000	300000
37	2	240000	7	2	350000	350000
38	2	240000	4	1	240000	240000
39	0	200000	10	2	150000	299000

Table 2: Correlation Coefficients of dependent and independent variables by Pearson Correlation

Source: Based on Table 1

Correlations

			X0 No. of school children	X1 income head	X2 education of head	X3 No. of workers	X4 expenditure of the family	X5 income of the family
X0 No. of school children	Pears on Correlation		1	.204	-.051	.180	.222	.353*
	Sig. (2-tailed)			.219	.760	.279	.179	.030
	N		38	38	38	38	38	38
X1 income head	Pears on Correlation		.204	1	.052	.433**	.649**	.680**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.219		.757	.007	.000	.000
	N		38	38	38	38	38	38
X2 education of head	Pears on Correlation		-.051	.052	1	-.083	.120	.127
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.760	.757		.619	.473	.447
	N		38	38	38	38	38	38
X3 No. of workers	Pears on Correlation		.180	.433**	-.083	1	.480**	.556**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.279	.007	.619		.002	.000
	N		38	38	38	38	38	38
X4 expenditure of the family	Pears on Correlation		.222	.649**	.120	.480**	1	.798**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.179	.000	.473	.002		.000
	N		38	38	38	38	38	38
X5 income of the family	Pears on Correlation		.353*	.680**	.127	.556**	.798**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.030	.000	.447	.000	.000	
	N		38	38	38	38	38	38

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 3: Partial Correlation Coefficients showing the effects of one or more additional variables on X_0

Source: Based on Table 1

Table 4: Partial Correlation Coefficients showing the effects of one or more additional variables on the number of the school children

Source: Based on Table 1

Correlations

Control Variables			X0 No. of school children	X2 education of head
X1 income head & X3 No. of workers & X4 expenditure of the family & X5 income of the family	X0 No. of school children	Correlation	1.000	-.107
		Significance (2-tailed)	.	.549
		df	0	32
	X2 education of head	Correlation	-.107	1.000
		Significance (2-tailed)	.549	.
		df	32	0

Objective 2

To study controlling factors on the income of the family

Hypothesis 2

- There is a relationship between the income of the family, X_0 and other 5 variables such as income of the head X_1 , educational background of the head, X_2 and the number of workers in the family, X_3 , their expenditures X_4 and the number of school children X_5 .

Multivariate analysis (Path analysis)

X_0 = the income of the family

X_1 = income of the head of the family

X_2 = educational background of the head

X_3 = the number of workers in the family

X_4 = expenditures

X_5 = the number of school children

Figure 5 : A set of hypothesis for a dependent variable, X_0

Source : Table 1

Path analysis is used to identify the relationships between variables. Here the dependent variable, X_0 is the income of the slum family.

If X_1 and X_3 increase, X_0 will increase and if X_0 increases, X_4 and X_5 will also have the same direction. It is also found that if X_2 increases, X_0 and X_1 will also do. However, X_2 and X_3 variables are negative relationship. Therefore, if education of the head is high, he can support the whole family and then number of workers in the family will decrease and the number of school children will rise. The important variables in the number of income of the family are to depend on the income of the head and the number of workers. Income of the head is more influent than the number of workers to increase X_0 . So, the income of the head is a vital role in a slum family. His educational background supports partly (Figure 5).

Aim - to analyse the responsible factors for the emergence and growth of slums in the study area

Qualitative method is used to analyse the controlling factors for the emergence and growth of slum settlement. The field survey is carried out within 1994 to 2000, 2001 to 2010 and 2011 to 2017 which slum settlement started,

16% of slum settlement is found in the first period, 53% in the second period and 31% in the third period.

The researcher wanted to know why they become homeless. Since **before 2000**, slums migrated from North Okkalapa, Hlaingtharyar and Mingaladon Townships. There are many reasons to move here. Some were farmers and their farm land were taken over by the government so that they had to move to another place and then resettled here as slums. Some are guards in the compound, but the landowner sold the compound and the guards have become jobless and then they settled as slum dwellers.

Daw Aye Aye Khine who stays in “Thithat Lane 4” in Ward 1 as slum dweller said that “At first I rent a house in Ward 51 in Dagon Myothit East Township and then I came here to run a small rice shop, later I settle here as slum.”

They have never got government aid. Their future expectation for the family is to have own house.

Informal settlements sprang up **between 2001 and 2010**. They migrated from Rakhine State, Ayeyarwady Region and Other townships from Yangon Region such as Shwepyithar and the same Township (Dagon Myothit East). Slums who came from Ayeyarwady Region are mostly from Laputta Township because of the occurrence of natural disaster, Cyclone Nagic in 2008. Some people rent in the wards within this township (Dagon Myothit East) at first and they earn a little and they cannot afford to rent and become homeless people later. Monastery from this Township informed them to settle as slums. Another reason is that they have to pay the rent to the head of the Ward for every month to live here and later they did not have to pay and become slum dwellers. Some are informed by the head of the Ward.

As government officials' support, they help medicines for health of children and spray insect killer and hold 'talk for knowledge dissemination'.

Their future expectation is to have own house, children to be educated, and just to continue to stay here.

People who settled as slums **after 2011** came from various places. They migrated from Rakhine State, Ayeyarwady Region and townships from Yangon Region because of the information from the friends and monks in this township to stay as slums. Some people sold their house from other township and rent in a Ward in this township, but they cannot afford the rent and become homeless people. At first, they have to pay the rent to the head of the Ward Kyat 15,000 for 6 months as a donation to the Ward. However, they do not need to pay later and become slums.

Ko Thet Naing who stays near dumping ground said that "We stayed in Kwinkone village in Laputta Township in Ayeyarwady Region before 2008. After Nargic, we had difficulties to continue to survive because we did not have a house to stay in our native land and became jobless. At that time the monk informs his villagers to come and stay here. So, we settle here to make money by collecting waste materials and trade in them for money (Plate 4 and 5)."

Government supports them; helping medicines for health of children and spraying insect killer the areas surrounding their houses.

Future expectation of the slums is that they want a real estate, and children to be educated.

Plate 4 and 5 : Slum Settlements in Ward No. 1 in Dagon Myothit (East) Township
Source : Photo taken in 2017

Conclusion

Slum settlement is fairly large in Ward 1 located in the southwestern end of Dagon Myothit (East) Township. Its number of slum is 9th largest among 28 slum wards and 1 village in Dagon Myothit (East). It is found that the study area has more slum density than population density as a result of having large dumping ground in the North of the Ward, having the large extended area in the Ward, bounded by populated townships; North Okkalapa Township in the North and Dagon Myothit (North) Township in the Southwestern part if Ward No. 1 compares to other wards nearby.

The main problems of poverty are that slums sold the land that supported by the government because of not having enough money to live on and they cannot afford to pay the rent and thus numbers of slum dwellers come and stay fallow land.

There are many reasons to become homeless people. They are working in poorly paid jobs such as workers in construction site, security guards at night, bus helpers, tri-Shaw drivers, working odd-job, road-side sellers, green grocers, waste collectors, plumbers and industrial machine repairers. Most of them finished basic education, but it is generally accepted that people with more education have higher earnings

In the country, primary schools are State-funded, but they cannot attend school because school-age children have to work for the family. Since the parents do not have education to improve their

quality, they do not understand the advantages of educating their children. They remain trapped in the cycle of poverty.

Discussion and Suggestions

Why do they become homeless people?

Emergence of slums

Research has shown that from 1994 to 2017 slum settlement in Dagon Myothit East Township is mainly based on the socio-economic factors such as commuting costs, access to the local public goods, social ties such as similar income-generating activities and suffering from natural disaster such as Nargic Cyclone in 2008. These findings accord with Abramo, 2009 and Takeuchi, 2006, in correspondence to Barnhardt, 2014 and concur with Napier, 2007.

Growth of slums

Growth of slums is the consequences of migration from poor rural settlement area to urban area, poor urban governance (it is compatible with Rajiv Awas Yojana in India in 2013) and people born within or in close proximity to slums (accord with UN Habitat, 2003).

How to improve their capacities?

Solution for present situation

Government should plan to give these slums some works which are relevant to their present education background. It should be completely free of charge and enables them to become professional at work. Moreover, government should get them a job to make money while they are learning. These are more effective, suitable and best ways rather than giving them smart cards to move to low-value housing.

Solution for long-term

As a result of poor quality of education, uneducated parents are more focused on their short-term needs and neglects the long-term benefits of education and thus pull their children out of school to go to work.

All school-age children need to complete their education which is the best long-term solution to the problem of poverty, especially in poor communities and thus should focus on primary education at first. For this, government should plan not to lose of the labour forces of the family.

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ဒဂုံမြို့သစ်အရှေ့ပိုင်းမြို့နယ် အစီရင်ခံစာ၊ ၂၀၁၄ ခုနှစ် မြန်မာနိုင်ငံလူဦးရေနှင့် အိမ်အကြောင်းအရာ သန်းခေါင်စာရင်း၊ ရန်ကုန်တိုင်း၊ အရှေ့ပိုင်းခရိုင်